

Thematic Limitations in Academic Publishing: A Scenario in Humanities Academic Development by Sun

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While there are overlaps between academic and social pursuits, Sun is a PhD candidate ,and she confronted a bottleneck in the realm of academic publishing. The prevailing focal point in social science academia is artificial intelligence, implying that the trajectory of the next era is closely intertwined with AI. However, Sun's field of study exhibits limited relevance to this burgeoning theme. Upon submitting her article, the editor expressed the desire for Sun to align her theme with the current societal hot topic, emphasizing that failure to do so might preclude publication in the journal. This predicament extends beyond a singular authoritative journal.

This situation prompts the question:

1. Is the merit of academic publication and research contingent on social trends or the intrinsic value of the research itself?
2. Must scholars, like Sun, engage with prevailing societal interests to bolster their academic standing through publication?
3. Navigating this challenge requires scholars to strike a balance between addressing contemporary societal concerns and pursuing topics with enduring academic significance. How can scholars reconcile these competing demands within their academic endeavors?